

Physical Properties of n-Saturated Higher Fatty Alcohols in Liquid State

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Density, refractive index and viscosity of n-saturated fatty alcohols in liquid state were determined and compared with those of fatty acids having the same number of C-atoms as well as their methyl esters. The effect of chain length and temperature on the properties are discussed. In the alcohol series, the density increases as the series is ascended while it decreases in the other two.

THE density²⁻⁵, refractive index²⁻⁷ and viscosity^{4,7-11} data of n-saturated fatty acids and their methyl esters were reported earlier but the physical properties of fatty alcohols were performed at arbitrary temperatures and that too mostly for even-chain fatty alcohols^{1,2}. Systematic data on these are important for plant design purposes, and hence the present investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

The glc- and tlc-pure n-saturated fatty alcohols (from undecanyl through nonadecanyl), fatty acids and fatty acid methyl esters used were the same as reported in a previous communication¹. The procedure followed for the determination of density (d), refractive index (RI) and viscosity (η) at different temperatures, above the respective m.p., are exactly the same as those described earlier^{1,8}.

Results and Discussion

Density: The density of each compound is determined, at interval of 5°, at five different temperatures in liquid state for fatty alcohols, fatty acids and methyl esters, and for all the series density decreases linearly with temperature (Fig. not shown for brevity). The temperature coefficient of density (m) and the theoretical density (c) of the equation,

$$\text{Density} = mt + c$$

where, t is the temperature (°C), were calculated by the method of least-squares (Table 1). The value of m decreases marginally as the series are ascended; the average value for fatty alcohols (6.86×10^{-4}) is somewhat lower than that for fatty acids (7.50×10^{-4}) and their methyl esters (7.60×10^{-4}). The highly significant coefficient of linear correlation, for all the nine homologues, calculated from density data at different temperatures, ranged from -0.99714 to -0.99992 .

As can be seen from the calculated values of c , at any given temperature, the density of any fatty alcohols is lower than that of the fatty acid having the same number of C-atoms while the value of the methyl ester of the latter is in between the two. Further, in the fatty alcohol series, the density decreases as the series is ascended while in the other two it increases; these differences are, no doubt, due to the varying influence of the polar group at the end of long hydrocarbon chain on the Packing density in liquid state. Eventhough the change in density with increase in molecular weight are not exactly linear, at any given temperature, the changes in molar volume (calculated from data) per added CH_2 -group are constant; the average change in molar volume for fatty alcohols at 80° is 17.06 and is slightly lower than those of fatty acid and methyl ester series (17.25 for both).

Refractive index (RI): The RI data are obtained for all the fatty alcohols in liquid state at five temperatures with interval of 5°. The plots of RI against temperature follow linear relationship (Fig. not shown for brevity). The temperature coefficient (m') and the index of refraction at 0° (c') in the equation $\text{RI} = m't + c'$, are calculated by the method of least squares (Table 1). Like for fatty acids and their methyl esters^{2,8}, the RI of an alcohol decreases as the temperature increases, the average value m' is 3.76×10^{-4} . The highly significant coefficient of linear correlation, for all the nine homologues of fatty alcohol series, calculated from RI data at different temperatures ranged from -0.98704 to -0.99996 .

At any given temperature, as the series is ascended, the increase in RI is progressive but nonlinear. Molar refraction changes progressively; the average increase in molar refraction due to addition of CH_2 -group calculated from determined data for fatty alcohols, is 4.62, and this compares well with the reported values^{2,8} for the fatty acids (4.65) and methyl esters (4.64).

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF CONSTANTS FOR DENSITY AND REFRACTIVE INDEX

No. of C-atoms in compd.*	Data for density Fatty alcohols		Data for RI for Fatty alcohols		Data for density Fatty acids		Data for density Fatty acid methyl esters	
	$-m$	c	$-m'$	c'	$-m$	c	$-m$	c
	$\times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$	g cm^{-3}	$\times 10^{-4}$		$\times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$	g cm^{-3}	$\times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-3} \text{ K}^{-1}$	g cm^{-3}
11	7.00	0.846 8	3.95	1.450 0	7.60	0.912 1	7.55	0.883 8
12	6.94	0.847 1	3.90	1.451 7	7.52	0.908 1	7.65	0.883 3
13	6.78	0.848 1	3.85	1.453 3	7.50	0.906 5	7.64	0.882 7
14	6.86	0.850 1	3.80	1.454 9	7.50	0.904 3	7.64	0.882 4
15	6.88	0.851 5	3.75	1.456 3	7.50	0.901 7	7.62	0.881 8
16	6.82	0.852 3	3.73	1.457 8	7.50	0.900 8	7.60	0.881 4
17	6.82	0.854 0	3.67	1.458 9	7.48	0.898 5	7.55	0.880 6
18	6.80	0.855 6	3.62	1.459 9	7.46	0.896 9	7.50	0.879 7
19	6.80	0.857 4	3.55	1.461 0	7.45	0.895 5	7.50	0.879 4

*C-atom of methyl group of fatty acid ester is not counted.

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY (cp) DATA

No. of C-atoms in alkyl/acetyl-chain	Viscosity of fatty alcohols at ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)					Viscosity of fatty acids at 80°	Viscosity of methyl esters at 80°	$A \times 10^4$	B
	60	65	70	75	80				
11	4.35	3.75	3.42	2.86	2.50	2.95	1.05	2.76	6 402
12	4.99	4.31	3.71	3.26	2.86	3.26	1.19	2.58	6 544
13	5.61	4.91	4.21	3.72	3.20	4.02	1.32	2.34	6 691
14	6.67	5.75	4.98	4.37	3.73	4.44	1.50	2.26	6 824
15	7.80	6.35	5.45	4.70	4.10	5.16	1.75	2.20	6 903
16	8.32	7.01	6.07	5.22	4.55	5.91	2.00	2.08	7 021
17	8.75	7.79	6.60	5.69	4.88	6.70	2.20	1.81	7 178
18	9.45	8.55	7.40	6.35	5.52	7.75	2.47	1.78	7 266
19	—	9.44	8.15	7.01	6.10	8.61	2.81	1.73	7 363

Viscosity(η): The viscosity data for fatty alcohols at different temperatures at intervals of 5° are given in Table 2; for comparison, the determined data at 80° for fatty acids and methyl esters are also given. As can be expected, the viscosity decreases nonlinearly with increase in temperature, and so also with the decrease in the alkyl chain length. From the kinetic theory of viscosity of liquids¹⁴, the following expression may be derived,

$$\eta = A e^{B/RT}$$

where, A and B are constants, T is the absolute temperature, R the universal gas constant and η the viscosity of the liquid. Therefore, a plot of $\ln \eta$ against $1/T$ results in a straight line, yielding A as intercept and B/R as slope. Fig. 1 shows nine such straight lines for the different alcohols investigated, and the values of A and B are given in Table 2. According to the kinetic theory of liquids, the constant A depends on the packing characteristics of molecules and the molar volume. As a matter of fact, A is inversely proportional to molar volume in a homologous series. Hence it is expected that the value of A should decrease with the increase in chain length. On the other hand, constant B depends on characteristic free energy which may be related to the internal energy for evaporation. As the boiling point and heat of vapourisation increase with the increasing chain length, constant B should also increase as the series is ascended. The present data (Table 2) show this trend. At 80° , fatty alcohols have viscosity in between that of fatty acids and

Fig. 1. Plots of log viscosity of fatty alcohols vs reciprocal of absolute temperature.

methyl esters showing the influence of the type of terminal polar group on flow properties of liquids having long hydrocarbon chains.

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References

1. B. R. GAIKWAD and V. V. R. SUBRAHMANYAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 518.
2. A. DORINSON, M. R. MCÓORKLE and A. W. RALSTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2739.
3. E. G. HAMMOND and W. O. LUNDBERG, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **31**, 427.
4. A. T. GROS and R. O. FRUGE, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 313.
5. T. H. GOUW and J. C. VLUGTER, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 142.
6. T. H. GOUW and J. C. VLUGTER, *Fette Seifen. Anstrichm.*, 1966, **68**, 544.
7. B. M. CRAIG, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1953, **35**, 499.
8. A. E. DUNSTAN, F. B. THOLE and P. BENSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 782.
9. A. E. DUNSTAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 667.
10. C. W. BONHORAT, P. M. ALTHOUSE and H. O. TRIBOLD, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1948, **40**, 2729.
11. T. H. GOUW, J. C. VLUGTER and C. J. A. ROELANDS, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 433.
12. V. MAHADEVAN in "Progress in the Chemistry of Fats and Other Lipids", ed. R. T. HOLMAN, Pergamon, New York, 1979, Vol. 15, p. 255.
13. I. G. THAPAR and V. V. R. SUBRAHMANYAM, *J. Oil Technol. Assoc. India*, 1979, **5**, 36.
14. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, "Theory of Rate Process", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, Chap. 9.